

NON-HUMAN LIFE FORMS

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You are a non-human living being, who inhabits this space. You are part of the urban ecosystem.

Do you live here or are you migrating or are you passing through?

You are the trees, birds, the waterways, the flowerbeds, moss, and more.

UNCOMMON CROWD

NON-HUMAN MACHINES

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You are a non-human entity situated in the city with the power to sense, and collect information from your environment.

You can be part of another machine that makes it a 'smart' (IoT) device, you could be a boat cruising through a canal or a node in a network of smart doorbells.

UNCOMMON CROWD

RESIDENTS

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You are a person who inhabits this space, you live and/or work here.

You are tuned in to the changes of the place, you notice the small details, like the cracks in the pavement when others don't.

You care for your community and committed to its flourishing.

UNCOMMON CROWD

GUESTS

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You are an individual visiting the area or who transits through here.

Passing through is a part of how you experience the city.

You are less aware of the ins and outs of what happens here. The particularities of the place can at times escape you.

UNCOMMON CROWD

INVESTORS

INVESTORS

You have a birds eye view of what goes on here. You represent an entity that invests in the 'smart' updating and success of this place.

You are interested in specific details of how this place is managed, monitored, and optimised over time.

Data is gold for you.

UNCOMMON CROWD

STEWARDS

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You operate as a care taker, shaping decisions from caring for the streets to shaping public policies.

You are an expert on how the city runs and the value of data in making it more resilient and adaptive to change.

You advocate for alternative data ownership models.

UNCOMMON CROWD

